

ISic1206

Epitaph for Diokles

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Given to the Palermo museum by A. Campo of Tripi in the 1880s, exact provenance not recorded

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8703

Physical Description

A small cippus, broken below, some damage to the right edge.

Dimensions

Height 24 cm
Width 26.5 cm
Depth 14 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Crude and irregular letters of unequal size, deeply incised. Omicron is small and mid-line; kappa has short equal length arms attached to the vertical; epsilon has shorter middle bar (i the first instance detached from the vertical); alpha has straight bar; rho has rounded closed eye.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 30-75 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Δίοκλε
2. χᾶϊρε

Apparatus

Text as per IG and IGMusPal

Translation (en)

Diokles, farewell!

Commentary

The name is in the vocative form of Διοκλῆς [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%94%CE%B9%CE%BF%CE%BA%CE%BB%E1%BF%86%CF%82], a common name, widely attested in Sicily. The suggestion of Manni Piraino that it derives from a form Δίοκλος (suggested to be attested by Cic. Verr. 2.5.16 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi0474.phi005.perseus-eng1:2.5.16>]: de Apollonio, Dioclii filio, Panhormitano, cui gemino cognomen est) seems implausible. The form Δίοκλος [<http://www.igpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V3b-37428>] is only attested once, and the form in the Verrines is surely a latinisation of convenience. There is no obvious reason to date this to the early imperial period (as Manni Piraino does); the letter forms - as well as the contextual evidence of the Hellenistic necropolis at Abakainon - suggest a Hellenistic date.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492810

EDR 147871

EDCS 39101570

PHI 140690

PHI 175728

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1206>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4022630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022630)

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0382a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelika 6.* Palermo. At 125

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 464 no.d

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. *Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften.* Göttingen. At 5208a

Sofia, G. 2015. *Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME).* At 108 and fig.112

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1206. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). [http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4352212](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4352212)